

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NUTRITIONAL REHABILITATION AMONG MALNOURISHED CHILDREN ADMITTED IN A SELECTED HOSPITAL, VADODARA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Over the last 30 years, there has been a dramatic decrease in the prevalence of malnutrition. It's still a major source of sickness and mortality for children all throughout the world, but it's even more so in nations with poor and middle incomes. Mortality rates from marasmus and kwashiorkor are high. Only a small percentage of malnourished children have access to treatment because of treatment methods. Moreover, treating children with severe malnutrition who need to be hospitalized is a difficult clinical issue that must be overcome. *Aims and Objectives:* Nutritional rehabilitation efficacy was evaluated, as well as the relationship between nutritional status and a number of demographic variables among children admitted to a particular hospital. *Materials & Methods:* This study took a quantitative approach. A study was carried out in a Vadodara hospital's Nutritional rehabilitation center. The researcher went with a one-group pre-test-post-test design for their pre-experimental research. The effectiveness of nutritional rehabilitation in malnourished children was examined using a non-probability purposeful sampling technique on a group of 30 malnourished children. *Results:* Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the collected data. The Nutritional rehabilitation was found to be significant because the obtained t value 14 was higher than the table value of t (2.43) at a 0.05 level and with 29 degrees of freedom. As a result, H01 was approved. The obtained X2 value of demographic variables is less than the 0.05 level of significance of the table value of X2 0.05. As a result, the resulting X2 value is of no consequence. Demographic data did not correlate with Nutritional Status, therefore. *Conclusion:* It can be concluded that nutritional rehabilitation is effective in improving the nutritional status of malnourished children.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Assess, Malnutrition, Nutritional rehabilitation

1. Introduction

Malnutrition occurs when a child's food intake falls short of what the body requires to operate normally, resulting in stunted growth and development. A child's risk of malnutrition increases when they have a chronic condition. Early diagnosis, prevention, and therapy of malnutrition are critical for children's rapid growth and development. In children with chronic diseases, there are several causes of malnutrition, including the disease itself as well as factors unrelated to sickness. In this review, malnutrition in children with a congenital cardiac condition will be discussed in relation to the etiology, evaluation, and management of the condition.

Children with severe malnutrition and acute illnesses such as diarrhea can be treated more successfully with fewer deaths, morbidities, and costs by starting treatment with appropriate nutrition, supplementing with micronutrients, using broad-spectrum antibiotics, and managing complications carefully. This study discusses a structured approach for treating extremely malnourished children with acute

diseases, such as diarrhea, based on the previously described variables. The protocol's implementation reduced these children's mortality by 47% beginning in professional philosophy for the last hundred years, but now moral philosophers find themselves at the center of the medical field.

Medical ethics examines the characteristics of medical morality, playing a particularly important role in shaping the principles on which the moral code of medical professionals is based. To be a qualified physician means not only having excellent knowledge of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, but also a proper outlook, the basis of which should be humanism, high culture, ability to communicate, and a sense of pride in participation in the medical industry (Rambu, Fedchyshyn, & Permiakova, 2019).

The teaching of ethical theory and its relevance in the form of lectures began back in the 1970s and 1980s (Beauchamp, & Childress, 2019). The course was designed for scientists, physicians, nurses, public policy experts, and others.

The first introductions of bioethics as an

academic discipline took place in the 1990s before Muaygil (2020). However, the growth of interest was very slow and incomprehensible due to the growth of medical research and the empirical base focused on medical practice and the absence of academic departments and an overwhelming number of self-educated teachers, only some of whom had formal education. Gradually, seminars and conferences related to bioethical issues grew, as did postgraduate research and education, indicating the growing interest indicated by Muaygil (2020). It should be noted that the study of these academic disciplines plays an important role in the humanities education of the modern doctor, as they fulfill a threefold purpose: to describe, explain and teach morals and ethical behavior.

SAM in children is a major public health issue in India, and it's linked to higher rates of morbidity and mortality. According to the World Health Organization, the best way to treat Patients with SAM will be treated in a hospital setting with a specialized programme. With so many children in India suffering from severe asthma and the associated costs for care providers and patients, it's critical to include alternative treatments like home-based management of simple SAM. Home-based treatment for SAM using therapeutic nutrition products (RUTF) is effective and safe, according to this review.

Stabilization and rehabilitation are the two phases of treatment for children with SAM. Treatment is required during the early stabilization phase for children with dehydration, electrolyte abnormalities, concurrent infections, and other issues. This stage is all about catching up growth, so the recommended calorie and protein intake is much higher (applicable to children with straightforward SAM or those with complex SAM after issues have been overcome). Home-based treatment may be a better option for children with SAM who cannot or do not want to receive therapy in a hospital setting. However, in our previous analysis, we found no solid evidence that ready-to-use therapeutic food was effective (RUTF). This investigation is necessary, and it must be done immediately. Malnutrition, according to the World Health Organization, is when a person's energy and/or

nutrient intake is inadequate, excessive, or out of balance. In the long run, this will affect the child's socioeconomic status. Several organizations, including the National Health and Family Survey, the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, and the World Health Organization, have documented an unacceptable rate of malnutrition in India. Maternal nutrition, lactation behavior, education of women, and sanitary conditions contribute to the country's malnutrition. The negative effects on children include stunting, childhood illness, and stunted growth. In spite of the nominal decline in India's malnutrition rate over the last decade and the implementation of numerous government programs, research-based knowledge gained from studies is still urgently needed to combat the countries chronic under nutrition problem. They may be useful for other developing countries working to combat child malnutrition. 5

This study was conducted under controlled conditions, including the use of malnutrition stickers and evaluations by 16 dieticians, which should be noted. It's an ideal situation, but it's not always the case. In "usual care," factors affecting the detection of malnutrition include the low completion rate of malnutrition screening by the nursing staff, low referral rates for dieticians, and patients who are discharged before being assessed by the dietician. "Usual care" may explain some of the differences in malnutrition coding between the groups. The previous and current generations.

2. Objectives of the study

- To Assess the Nutritional Status of Malnourished children.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of nutritional rehabilitation.
- To find out the association between the nutritional status and selected demographic variables of children admitted in selected hospital.

Hypothesis

H01: There was a significant improvement in the nutritional status of children after nutritional rehabilitation.

3. Materials and Methods

Research Approach: Quantitative research approach was used to assess the malnourished children who is hospitalized in NRC.

Research Design: A Pre experimental research design was used to assess nutritional rehabilitation, among malnourished children in selected hospitals of Vadodara.

Place of Study: The study was conducted in Dhiraj General Hospital.

Source of Data: Malnourished children admitted in Nutritional Rehabilitation Centre.

Population:

Accessible population: Children admitted in NRC who are eligible for sample as per inclusion criteria.

Sampling Technique and Size: In this study, Non- Probability purposive sampling technique was used. 30 children were selected from NRC of Dhiraj hospital.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Malnourished children admitted in NRC.
- Malnourished children admitted in NRC at least two week of hospitalization experience.
- Parents of children, who can read, write, speak and understand Gujarati and English language.

Equipment for the Study

- Tool for data collection: Nutritional assessment scale

$\frac{\text{Actual weight}}{\text{Expected weight}} \times 100$

IAP Classification:

Weight For Age	Nutritional Grade
≥80	Normal
70-89.9	Grade 1 (Mild Undernutrition)
60-69.9	Grade 2 (Moderate Undernutrition)
50-59.9	Grade 3 (Severe Undernutrition)
<50	Grade 4 (Severe Undernutrition)

4. Results

This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data collected from 30 A study to assess effectiveness in nutritional rehabilitation of malnourished children

admitted in selected hospital in Vadodara. The data were analyzed according to the objectives of the study in three parts.

- Assess the Nutritional Status of Malnourished children by Pre - test
- Evaluate the effectiveness of nutritional rehabilitation by Post-Test.
- Find out the association between the nutritional status and selected demographic variable of children admitted in selected hospital.

Assess the Nutritional Status of Malnourished Children

Categories	f	%	
Admission Grade	Grade-2	9	30
	Grade -3	14	46.7
	Grade -4	7	23.3

Distribution of Admission Grade

Table shows the 9(30%) belongs to grade-2, 14(46.7%) belongs to grade-3, 7(23.3%) belongs to grade-4.

Categories	f	%	
Discharge Grade	Grade-1	9	30
	Grade -2	12	40
	Grade -3	9	30

Distribution of Discharge Grade

Table shows, 9(30%) belongs to grade-1,12(40%) belongs to grade-2 , 9(30%) belongs to grade-3.

Evaluate the effectiveness of nutritional rehabilitation by Post-Test.

Effectiveness	M	Differnece	SD	t
Adm. Grade	2.93	0.93	0.73	14
Dis. Grade	2.00		0.78	

$df - 29, t - 2.043$ (At 0.05 level)

As the obtained t value 14 was found higher than the table value of t (2.43) at 0.05 level and 29 degree of freedom, the Nutritional rehabilitation was found to be effective. Thus H01 was accepted.

Find out the association between the nutritional status and selected demographic variable of children admitted in selected hospital.

The obtained X2 value in all variables are less than the table value of X2 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the obtained X2 value is not Significant. There is no association between selected demographic variables and Questionnaire.

5. Discussion

The study's findings have been discussed in light of the goals and supporting research.

The first goal was to determine whether or not nutrition was effective during the rehabilitation process. Using the obtained t value 14, it was discovered that it was higher than the table value of t (2.43) at the 0.05 level with 29 degrees of freedom.

The second goal was to see if the nutritional status of children admitted to a particular hospital was linked to certain demographic variables.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the collected data. The Nutritional rehabilitation was found to be significant because the obtained t value 14 was higher than the table value of t (2.43) at 0.05 level and 29 degree of freedom. As a result, H01 was approved. It was found that the X2 value of demographic variables obtained was less than

the threshold value of 0.05. As a result, the resulting X2 value is of no consequence. No connection could be found between the demographics and Nutritional Status.

6. Conclusion

The focus in this study was evaluating the effectiveness of nutrition rehabilitation in malnourished children at Dhiraj general hospital,

The output indicated the nutritional rehabilitation was successful. Majority of the children who were admitted in the Nutritional rehabilitation centre were benefitted which showed in their discharge grade as the majority progressed to Grade 1 and Grade 2.

7. Conflict of Interest

There were no conflict of interest pertaining to this study

References

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